

Monkey Pox: A Review on Existing Scenario

Anil A¹, Saravanan A¹, Kumar T², Dutta G³, Vinoth R³, Singh S⁴, Varthya SB⁵

¹Junior Resident, Department of Pharmacology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

³Senior Resident, Department of Community Medicine and Family Medicine, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

⁴Additional Professor, Department of Pharmacology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

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Corresponding author: Dr Kumar T

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Abstract

Monkeypox is an uncommon zoonotic viral infection with symptoms similar to smallpox but with less severe clinical presentation. The term 'Monkeypox' was coined in 1958 following its discovery from the colonies of laboratory monkeys. It is endemic in some African countries. Following the outbreak in 2022, WHO declared monkeypox as a global public health emergency on 23rd July 2022. 12 cases have been recorded in India till 24th September 2022. Despite the incidence of cases, outbreak preparedness by the WHO and national governments have contributed greatly to reduce the infectivity of this disease. Literatures from online databases such as PubMed, CENTRAL, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar and International Guidelines were searched for the articles. A total of 33 articles and websites were utilized to concise the quality information about this emerging disease.

Keywords: Monkey-pox, Pox Virus, Review, Public Health.

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Introduction

Monkeypox (MPX) is an uncommon zoonosis of viral origin with symptoms that are similar to smallpox but with less severe clinical presentation. Ever since smallpox had been eradicated in the year 1980 and the smallpox vaccinations were discontinued, monkeypox became the most significant orthopoxvirus for public health [1-3]. In the year 1958, Monkeypox was identified in the colonies of monkeys that were held for

research purposes, hence termed as "Monkeypox".

The morphology of Poxvirus is characterized by a brick-shaped structure with linear double-stranded DNA genome that is encased within the envelope of lipoprotein [4,5]. The first reported monkeypox case was a 9 year old child who was not vaccinated for smallpox, from Democratic Republic of the Congo. Most of the monkeypox cases were

found in Central and West Africa [1] Monkeypox case outside of African countries was first reported in the year 2003, which was found to be due to contact with pet prairie dogs that had monkeypox.

These dogs were accommodated with dormice and pouched rats that were imported from Ghana that were from the Gambia [6] From few to hundreds of lesions may be present overall [7]. Patient will become non-contagious, when all the crusts from the lesions fall off [8].

Monkeypox is diagnosed by the detection of the viral DNA from the lesions [9]. The illness can also resemble chickenpox in appearance [7] The efficacy of the smallpox vaccine is 85% [10,11].

Morphology of monkey pox virus

Monkeypox is a member of the family Poxviridae, subfamily of chordopoxvirinae, orthopoxvirus genus and monkeypox virus species [12] When viewed using an electron microscope, the size of the virus is quite large, around 200 to 250 nanometres. It is brick-shaped and with linear double-stranded DNA genome enclosed in a sheath of lipoprotein [4,5] Poxvirus genome also contains proteins for replication, transcription, assembly, and egression, in addition to the fact that poxviruses rely on host ribosomes for mRNA translation [4,13]

Epidemiology

It is endemic central and west Africa, mainly in the rain forests of those nations. The term 'monkeypox' was coined as it was first found in 1958 in laboratory monkeys. A proportion of African rodents had monkeypox infection, as evidenced by later blood testing on animals from that continent. When the virus was discovered among people residing in remote African locales, first monkeypox case in humans was identified in 1970. From 1981 to 1986, Democratic Republic of the Congo reported 37 monkeypox cases. The same

location reported a sizable monkeypox outbreak between February 1996 and February 1997.

There was an outbreak in United States (Wisconsin, Illinois, and Indiana) in 2003, which occurred around the time of emergence of an unknown infectious disease called severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) which was identified first in China and eventually spread worldwide in a short period of time [14]. The number of affected cases has increased at least ten times, and the common age of presentation shifted from 4 years old children in the year 1970 to 21 years old adults between 2010 and 2019. This was attributed to the removal of smallpox immunizations, which rendered cross-protection against the monkeypox virus [15]. A significant 2017 epidemic in Nigeria, with around 146 suspected monkeypox cases and 42 laboratory-confirmed cases, happened around 40 years after the last case of the country was recorded in 1978 [16].

Current status of 2022 outbreak

On 23th July 2022, monkeypox epidemic was categorized under global public health emergency by World Health Organization (WHO), which is considered as the greatest level of risk that an organization can place on epidemics or pandemics. 65295 confirmed cases from 105 countries, along with 26 fatalities, were reported to WHO as of September 26, 2022. Twelve cases have been recorded from India as of September 24, 2022. Kerala, an Indian state, reported the country's first case on July 14, 2022 [17].

Transmission and affected species

Rodents are thought to be the main vector for the virus's human transmission. Despite the fact that monkeypox disease has resurfaced in humans, the natural animal reservoir for the virus haven't been discovered yet. As a result, it is not known whether human behaviours contribute to early virus

transmission from animals to humans. It can transmit from one animal to another animal hence, the ability of the spread of infection to human is possible. Such incidents involving the infection of people, including children, by prairie dogs have been documented from the United States (US). It was discovered that the rodents that were shipped from Ghana to the US infected these dogs [18].

Genital lesions revealed that the virus most likely transmitted by close physical contact [19]. Majority of the cases involved young men, mostly those men who had sex with other men (MSM). All mammals are susceptible to monkeypox infection. Numerous animal species such as rodents (mice, rats, prairie dogs and squirrels), rabbits, pigs and old and new world monkeys and apes (rhesus macaques, langurs, baboons, cynomolgus monkeys, chimpanzees, gorillas, orangutans, marmosets and gibbons) have been reported to be infected with the virus. No occurrences have had an impact on cats or dogs. It's still unclear what monkeypox's natural reservoirs are. The two African squirrel species, *Funisciurus anerythrus* and *Heliosciurus rufobrachium* are being suggested as potential reservoirs or vectors. It is unknown whether primates are incidental hosts or whether they sustain the infection viable in the wild [1,20]. Humans can contract monkeypox by infected objects, respiratory droplets, or direct contact [2,21,22].

Clinical features

The symptoms of monkeypox last for two to four weeks on average and take four to fourteen days on average to appear [2,3]. When symptoms first appear, the infectious phase will start, and last until the rash heals, followed by all the scabs falling off and new skin layer will grow over the lesion [8],

Monkey pox can result in a wide range of signs and symptoms, from minor ailments that don't require medical attention to serious

illnesses that do. Pregnant women, children, and people with impaired immune systems are considered high risk groups. The most frequent signs and symptoms of monkeypox during the 2022 outbreak were headache, muscle aches, back pain, fever, chills, respiratory symptoms and swollen lymph nodes which were often followed by or coincided with the appearance of skin rashes that could last for two to three weeks.

The face, soles, palms, groin, genital, and/or anal regions might all be affected by the rash. Additionally, it may appear on the eyes, in the mouth, throat, vagina, or anus. There may be a single sore or as many as a thousand. A sore will start out as a flat skin lesion, fill with liquid, and then create a crust. This crust will eventually dry and fall off revealing new skin layer underneath [7].

Diagnosis

A person is more likely to have the illness if history of exposure is present or history of travel to areas where monkeypox is endemic [24]. For the polymerase chain reaction test, which has been used to diagnose monkeypox, fluid from the skin lesion is taken as a sample. If monkeypox infection is still thought to be present after a negative PCR result, further testing can be done to confirm the diagnosis [7]. These techniques include viral culture, electron microscopy, immunohistochemistry, and anti-orthopoxvirus IgG and IgM assays [7].

Management

A doctor should be consulted if you have symptoms of monkeypox or if you have come into contact with someone who is unwell. Most of the time, symptoms disappear on their own or with supportive treatment, such as painkillers or fever reducers. A person is infectious until all of the wound's crust and the scabs get peeled off, and a new skin layer form. Isolation, therefore, is advised during the infectious period. Anyone with

monkeypox should stay hydrated, consume a balanced diet, and get plenty of rest. Self-isolating individuals should take care of their mental health by engaging in activities that they find pleasurable and calming, maintaining in touch with loved ones via technology, and exercising if they feel well enough.

Keep skin dry and uncovered, prevent scratching the affected area, and take care of their rash by washing their hands before and after touching any sores (unless they are unavoidably in a room with someone else, in which case they should cover it with clothing or a bandage until they are able to isolate again). Sterilized water or an antiseptic solution can be used to keep the rash clean. Mouth sores can be treated with saltwater rinses, while body sores can be treated with warm baths with baking soda and Epsom salts. Serious monkeypox may be more common in children than in adults. Until they are well, they should be continuously watched in case they require more care.

It is still unclear if having had monkeypox in the past confers protection against subsequent infections, and if so, for how long. Some instances of secondary infections have been documented. Even if you've previously had monkeypox, you should take every precaution to prevent re-infection. European Medicines Agency (EMA) granted a special permission for the use of antivirals (such as Tecovirimat, intended to treat smallpox) to cure monkeypox in January 2022.

The following medical countermeasures are presently stocked in the Strategic National Stockpile (SNS) and could be used to treat the monkeypox, according to CDC [25].

1. The FDA and European Medicines Agency have granted approval to Tecovirimat for the treatment of adults and children with human smallpox illness brought on by the Variola

virus. Available as oral (200 mg pill) and intravenous tecovirimat injection [26].

2. The FDA has approved the drug Vaccinia Immune Globulin Intravenous (VIGIV) to treat vaccine-related adverse events. There is no evidence to support the use of VIGIV in the management of monkeypox, and it is unclear if VIGIV therapy will be beneficial for those with severe monkeypox infections. In severe circumstances, though, healthcare professionals might think about using it.

3. The FDA has given the antiviral medicine cidofovir (Vistide) approval for the treatment of cytomegalovirus retinitis among individuals with AIDS. The effectiveness of the drug, cidofovir in treating the monkeypox cases in human is still not known. However, in vitro tests and animal investigations demonstrated its efficacy against the orthopox viruses.

4. On June 4, 2021, the FDA approved brincidofovir, commonly known as CMX001 or Tembexa, for treating human smallpox illness in adults, new-borns and children. There are no statistics on how well brincidofovir works in treating people with monkeypox infection. However, in vitro tests and animal investigations have found it to be efficacious against the orthopox viruses. CDC is now running an Expanded Access Investigational New Drug (EA-IND) to make it easier to utilise brincidofovir as a monkeypox treatment.

Complications [27].

1. Death,
2. Bacterial skin superinfection,
3. Long-lasting scarring of skin,
4. Permanent scarring of cornea causing vision loss,
5. Hyper- or hypopigmentation,
6. Pneumonia,
7. Sepsis
8. Dehydration resulting in vomiting, diarrhoea, and painful oral lesions

leading to reduced oral intake, and widespread skin disruption leading to insensible loss of fluids.

9. Encephalitis

Preventive measures

Studies have demonstrated that smallpox immunisation effectively protects against monkeypox and other orthopoxvirus infections. Patients who are immunocompromised, however, run the danger of experiencing significant negative effects. Smallpox was eradicated in 1980, which resulted in the cessation of smallpox vaccination programmes, making a large population vulnerable to monkeypox. Two vaccines may be used for the prevention of monkeypox disease [28]. The JYNNEOS vaccine is authorised for the prevention of smallpox and monkeypox. The ACAM2000 vaccine is authorised for use as a smallpox vaccination and is made accessible for use as a monkeypox vaccine under the EA-IND process.

The recommended treatment for JYNNEOS uses a 0.5mL injection volume and a subcutaneous method of administration. An alternative regimen using intradermal delivery with an injection volume of 0.1mL may be utilised under an Emergency Use Authorization of the ongoing national public health emergency in United States (US) [28].

The clinical efficacy or effectiveness of the vaccines, JYNNEOS and ACAM 2000 in the ongoing outbreak is currently unknown [28].

JYNNEOS vaccine is currently in short supply both internationally and in US, although more production is anticipated in the upcoming weeks and months. ACAM2000 is widely available in the United States, however it has greater adverse effects and contraindications than other vaccines [28].

Steps taken by the government

1. Health care facilities should exercise extra caution when treating patients who exhibit an otherwise unexplainable rash, travelled within the previous 21 days to a nation with has a recent spike in confirmed cases or suspected individuals, or those in contact with someone who has the disease.
2. Until all the skin lesions are healed, and a new skin layer has grown, or the treating doctor has decided to cease the isolation, all the suspected individuals must be isolated at special medical facilities.
3. District Surveillance Officer of the Integrated Disease Surveillance Program must be notified about all such patients.
4. All infection control procedures must be used when caring for such patient.
5. In the event of a suspicion, laboratory samples including blood, sputum, vesicular fluid, etc. should be sent to NIV Pune for detection of monkeypox virus.
6. If a positive case is found, contact tracing must be started right away to find the patient's contacts during the previous 21 days [29].

On 19 August 2022, India launched its first RT-PCR kit for detection of monkeypox virus, made by Transasia Bio-Medicals. Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) has shown interest in making the Monkeypox virus isolates available for collaborations in the field of research and manufacturing activities, for the development of vaccines and diagnostic kit [30].

To track the prevalence of monkeypox in India, India authorized many viral research and diagnostic laboratories (VRDLs) dispersed around India [31].

Conclusion

Up until now, networks of men who have sex with other men have been primary foci in the multi-country 2022 monkeypox outbreak. To prevent a sustained spread of the disease into the general population, it is crucial to

comprehend instances in which people of different sexual orientation have contracted monkeypox [17]. The National AIDS Control Organization can boost the surveillance procedure for suspected monkeypox infections by screening all the at-risk groups such as MSM and female sex workers (FSW).

Indian Council of Medical Research - National Institute of Virology (ICMR-NIV) conducted research and commented that besides the screening of at-risk groups, following the COVID-19 protocol during air travel will also be advantageous in reducing the transmission among fellow passengers and personnel via respiratory droplets. Sudden disease outbreaks always lead to rise of misinformation and fear regarding the disease resulting in lot of conspiracy theories. To overcome false infodemics, the WHO acted fast and released information regarding the facts related to monkeypox, which would also help in controlling the disease in a better way [32].

Monkeypox started spreading globally around the time when there was an outbreak of tomato flu in India [33]. Hence, immediate actions to control the disease spread is vital for the government along with rapid release of facts of the disease and management guidelines to public and health care services, which will help healthcare workers, social workers and news agencies to disseminate factual information's and prevent panic situations among the general population [32].

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